

Exploring Citation Impact in Circular Economy Research: An Analysis of Expected Citations Based on LLM-Generated Lexical Similarities Between Papers

Niloufar Farrokhzad*, Mehmet Ali Abdulhayoglu** and Bart Thijs***

*niloufar.farrokhzad@kuleuven.be
<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-0995-8915>
KU Leuven, FEB, ECOOM, Belgium

**mehmet.abdulhayoglu@kuleuven.be
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1288-2181>
KU Leuven, FEB, ECOOM, Belgium

***bart.thijs@kuleuven.be
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0446-8332>
KU Leuven, FEB, ECOOM, Belgium

Abstract

We present a novel approach for estimating citation impact in circular economy research using Large Language Models to create lexical similarity relationships between papers. By applying cosine similarity, we weight the estimated citations at the paper level based on the citations of their most similar papers. This approach builds on the concept of related records and employs a bottom-up clustering methodology for citation-based assessments, enhancing the granularity and accuracy of bibliometric analysis. Our dataset consists of publications from 2001 to 2022 sourced from the Web of Science Core Collection and processed by ECOOM. Using this comprehensive dataset, we identify thematic clusters and ultimately refine citation estimations by accounting for publication year vicinity, cluster, and document type, ensuring the highest level of accuracy. This combined normalization strategy yielded improved results, providing a more nuanced understanding of citation impact in Circular Economy research.

1. Introduction

Assessing the impact of academic research necessitates a comprehensive evaluation of its influence, which is often measured by citation rates. However, conventional methods, such as journal-based or subject-based standards, may fail to capture the intricate contextual and thematic nuances that contribute to a paper's relevance and its subsequent citation potential. These traditional metrics often lack the necessary granularity, potentially overlooking subtle distinctions within a field and diminishing the accuracy of citation-based assessments. The problem has been acknowledged in the literature and several attempts have been made earlier e.g., implementation of fine-grained top-down clustering approaches have been proposed, where each paper is assigned to a single, fixed cluster. Yet, these methods struggle with papers that possibly span multiple topics, limiting flexibility for interdisciplinary research.

Our study endeavors to introduce a pioneering approach to estimating expected citation rates. Drawing inspiration from the environment-based citation normalization approach proposed by (Glänzel & Thijs, 2017), we seek to implement this methodology using lexical-similarity relations generated by Large Language Models.

When establishing citation indicator standards, we must recognize that patterns and practices vary within the same subject. Imposing a unified disciplinary standard based on cognitive classification overlooks these nuances. Therefore, two approaches are possible: the bottom-up

approach solution as proposed by Schubert and Braun (1986) by using related records as reference standards, and the top-down solution suggested by Waltman and Van Eck (2012) by clustering the document space "down" to the necessary micro-environments. Top-down high-resolution clustering enables fully automated processes to create unlabeled microenvironments, starting from the whole dataset and dividing it into smaller clusters. However, there are serious drawbacks like microclusters from static environments and large amounts of singletons and minute clusters. In contrast, in bottom-up approaches, documents are clustered based on organic relationships. This approach builds the clusters from the ground up, starting from individual papers and looking for direct relationships. Related-record-based environments serve as a promising alternative to cognitive subject categories in providing reference standards for citation rates of individual documents.

Following the proposed approach of (Schubert & Braun, 1993) for citation-based assessments using bibliographic coupling, we applied bottom-up clustering to organize the CE literature into meaningful environments based on their inherent semantic characteristics, avoiding reliance on preassigned subject categories or top-down expert-delineated topics. This clustering approach supports our primary goal of analyzing expected citation rates, as it offers a more contextual and broader perspective on the field's thematic diversity. By crafting these environments, we can assess expected citations based on lexical similarity within specific thematic clusters. Our research commences with a curated set of publications about the Circular Economy (CE), compiled within the framework of a domain study commissioned by the Flemish government to map related research activities. These publications represent a diverse, evolving, and highly multidisciplinary corpus.

Within this study, we present and analyze a novel method whereby LLMs generate embeddings for individual papers within the CE corpus, enabling the calculation of cosine similarities between them. Leveraging these embeddings, we construct a network that identifies the top 100 most lexically similar papers for each document. This similarity-based network forms the foundation for calculating expected citation rates.

By deriving expected citation rates from the cosine-weighted citation counts of these lexically similar papers, our approach offers a nuanced perspective on estimating the potential impact of research. By integrating context and meaning into the estimation process, we aim to provide a more comprehensive and accurate assessment of research impact.

2. Data and Methods

2.1. Data

The data for this study is sourced from the Web of Science Core Collection by Clarivate Analytics, covering bibliographic records from 2001 to 2022. The dataset was processed and cleaned at ECOOM, ensuring a high level of data quality and accuracy. To maintain a complete three-year citation window, the analysis is restricted to publications up to 2020.

The dataset includes citable documents such as articles, letters, notes, proceedings papers, and reviews. This core dataset was constructed using a detailed search strategy encompassing mandatory and optional keywords. This strategy was designed to cover a broad range of CE topics while reducing the risk of missing key research. It was validated through rigorous testing and domain expert feedback, ensuring both sensitivity and specificity.

To broaden the CE dataset, a citation-based expansion method was applied, including papers that either reference or are referenced by the initial core set. This approach captures a broader spectrum of the CE discourse, allowing the analysis to delve into the evolving understanding of the CE through a more interconnected research perspective.

2.2. Expected Citation Scores

In line with the methodology outlined by (Glänzel, Thijs, Schubert, & Debackere, 2009) , the normalization of citation impact and assessing expected citations in scientific research relies on several fundamental methodologies and metrics. These include:

- Observed Citation Rate: This metric reflects the factual citation impact of a unit, such as a country, region, or institution. The Mean Observed Citation Rate (MOCR) is quantified as the ratio of citation count to publication count.
- Mean Expected Citation Rate (MECR): MECR represents the average citation rate of all papers published in the same journal within the same year. While it can be calculated using different citation windows, consistency in the chosen window is crucial for meaningful comparisons. MECR is computed by aggregating impact measures (e.g., journal impact) and dividing by the number of papers.
- Field Expected Citation Rate (FECR): Similar to MECR, FECR focuses on subfields, providing the average citation rate of all papers published within the same subject in the same year.
- Normalized Mean Citation Rate (NMCR): NMCR measures the ratio of observed citation impact to field-based expected citation impact, thereby assessing citation rates against the standards established by specific subfields.
- Relative Citation Rate (RCR): RCR compares observed citation impact to journal-based expected citation impact, offering insight into the relative influence of a paper within its publication venue.

These metrics facilitate the normalization of citation rates by benchmarking against journal or subfield standards, but they may need redefinition. Journals function as small neighborhoods, while broader subfields encompass diverse areas with unique citation practices. This diversity necessitates reexamining traditional indicators to ensure they accurately reflect research impact across different citation practices.

2.2. LLM-Based Lexical Similarity

To capture semantic relationships among words and sentences in our corpus, we use LLMs to create embeddings, representing documents in a lower-dimensional space. Unlike traditional methods that rely on shared keywords, LLMs capture deeper contextual similarities, enabling us to identify similar documents even when they do not share exact words. We leverage LLMs, specifically all-MiniLM-L6-v22, to generate embeddings from the abstracts and titles of documents. This model's input token size of 512 tokens (approximately 350 words) is designed to efficiently understand and create embeddings that reflect the semantic meaning of short texts, such as abstracts and titles.

The embeddings are stored in ChromaDB, a vector database, to enable efficient similarity calculations. We use cosine similarity to measure the closeness between documents and determine the top 100 most similar publications for each document in our CE dataset. This threshold of 100 is derived from a distribution analysis, ensuring a balance in the breadth of our selection to avoid diluting the similarity measure's predictive power.

These similarity-based connections form the basis of a large-scale document network with over one million nodes. This network structure allows us to explore expected citation rates by examining cosine-weighted citation counts of these similar papers, providing a comprehensive framework for analyzing the citation impact of CE research. This approach offers a robust methodology for understanding how semantic relationships translate into citation patterns.

$$ECitRLLMs = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{100} cosine_i * cit_i}{\sum_{i=1}^{100} cosine_i}$$

2.3. Bottom-Up Clustering

We employed a modularity-based community detection technique to identify communities of documents sharing similar thematic content, in a bottom-up approach. This method assigns each document to a single community, resulting in 29 distinct clusters across 1.1 million publications spanning twenty years. This clustering methodology reveals cohesive groups of documents representing distinct topics within the CE-related literature.

After creating the clusters, we labeled them employing content analysis, which involved examining common keywords and central papers within each group. The labeling process provided insights into the underlying themes and allowed a deeper understanding of the topics prevalent in CE-related research. The labels (Appendix a.) reflect the diversity of the CE field, with some clusters exhibiting direct connections to CE topics and others exploring less intuitive themes.

The clusters also reveal varied patterns of citation and network-based characteristics, indicating robust and distinct thematic clustering. The majority of research activity within most clusters has occurred in the last five years, with 47% of documented efforts concentrated in this timeframe. Some clusters, like Cluster 18 on microplastics, have seen a significant focus on recent research (82% between 2018 and 2022), while others display a more balanced distribution across the study period.

3. Results and Discussion

In essence, for each paper in our corpus, we selected the 100 most lexically similar papers from the same dataset, with similarity measured using cosine similarity on their embeddings created by an LLM. We also identified 29 distinct clusters, each representing a thematic area within the CE literature, with each paper belonging to one cluster. The objective is to calculate the expected citations for each paper based on a weighted average of its most similar set of papers, with weights being the cosine similarity calculated between each pair of documents. We then analyze this ratio through the lens of thematic clusters over time.

Initially, we calculated LLM-based Expected citations at the paper level and then aggregated for a set e.g. the countries with a high share in CE literature, and compared them with Normalized Mean Citation Rate (NMCR) across those, to determine if this new metric correlates with the traditional method of calculating NMCR (Figure 1). The comparison between NMCR and LLM-based expected citation rates was made by a regression analysis, which yielded a correlation coefficient of 0.59 with a p-value of $2.378e-22$, suggesting a statistically significant relationship between these two variables. This result indicates a moderate positive correlation, implying that variations in NMCR are likely linked to changes in LLM-based expected citation rates.

Figure 1. Correlation Between NMCR and LLM-Based Expected Citations

Next, we need to be able to validate the scores by having a more fine-grained investigation, hence clustering, and to investigate the stability over time as networks are expanding. In Figure 2, we can see the ratio of actual citations to cosine-weighted expected citations across each cluster. In most clusters, during the early years, there's a noticeable overestimation (estimation values less than 1), which improves over time but tends to underestimate (estimation values greater than 1) in recent years. This may result from the trend of rapid growth and an increasing pattern of citations among most clusters, except for a few. The CE has rapidly evolved in recent years, with papers from 2021-2003 generally receiving fewer citations compared to those in later periods. This trend suggests that comparing each paper with others from the same period can lead to a more realistic estimation.

Figure 2. Cosine-Weighted Expected Citations Ratio

Cluster	2001-2003	2004-2006	2007-2009	2010-2012	2013-2015	2016-2018	2019-2021
0	0.5	0.57	0.67	0.69	0.79	0.91	1.1
1	0.75	0.83	0.88	0.91	0.9	0.95	1.02
2	0.84	0.92	1.05	0.97	0.9	0.89	0.87
3	0.45	0.52	0.59	0.68	0.79	1.05	1.12
4	0.22	0.31	0.52	0.67	0.85	1	1.03
5	0.49	0.58	0.74	0.76	0.83	0.94	0.89
6	0.54	0.64	0.78	0.8	0.83	0.93	1.09
7	0.48	0.61	0.67	0.75	0.73	0.89	1.02
8	0.73	0.75	0.81	0.74	0.8	0.88	1.07
9	0.79	0.78	1.08	0.99	0.89	0.83	0.81
10	0.88	0.88	0.85	0.89	0.91	0.92	0.88
11	0.29	0.34	0.5	0.58	0.71	0.95	1.24
12	0.27	0.35	0.57	0.6	0.72	0.91	1.15
13	1.06	0.78	0.79	0.81	0.77	0.83	1.11
14	0.99	0.9	0.88	0.85	0.83	0.8	0.9
15	0.48	0.58	0.79	0.7	0.73	0.86	1
16	0.62	0.72	0.76	0.77	0.77	0.9	1.14
17	0.68	0.8	0.82	0.88	0.93	1.03	1.06
18	0.42	0.61	0.75	0.7	0.8	0.93	1.08
19	0.59	0.65	0.89	0.85	0.81	0.8	0.92
20	0.31	0.37	0.65	1.05	0.94	0.95	0.8
21	0.21	0.3	0.48	0.51	0.65	0.94	1.05
22	0.37	0.5	0.63	0.76	0.93	0.98	1.01
23	0.36	0.42	0.8	0.93	0.77	0.73	0.96
24	0.52	0.64	0.66	0.66	0.8	1.01	1.01
25	0.74	0.77	0.86	0.88	0.96	1.14	1.05
26	1.04	0.79	1.56	0.92	0.93	0.87	0.83
27	0.42	0.6	0.63	0.67	0.84	1.03	1.13
28	0.17	0.22	0.34	0.4	0.73	1	1

Considering the entire CE period outside the lens of publication year windows, the weighted average tends to overestimate citation rates for papers in the CE by nearly 30%. This could be due to several reasons:

- 1- High-impact Paper Outliers: If highly cited papers within the top 100 similar papers significantly impact the estimated citation rate, it could skew the expected citation rate upwards. These papers might be outliers with exceptionally high citation counts, not due to lexical similarity but other factors like being authored by leading researchers in the field. Too many outliers with disproportionately high citations in each set can dilute the results.
- 2- Bias Towards High-Citation Papers: The LLM might unintentionally favor content from papers that are already well-cited. If high-citation papers tend to use certain keywords or phrases that become defining characteristics of what the model perceives as important within the dataset, the model could be more likely to select these papers as similar to others. In fields like CE, specific keywords might gain popularity at certain times. If our model is picking up on these popular terms or themes disproportionately, it might identify similarity based on these hot topics rather than broader, more genuine lexical similarity.
- 3- Common Themes and Vocabulary: High-citation papers might discuss cutting-edge topics or popular methodologies that set trends within the field. As these topics become

more prevalent, the vocabulary and context associated with them may also become more common in subsequent publications. Thus, a highly cited paper could set trends that influence the word choice criteria for lexical similarity in later papers.

- 4- **Comprehensive Abstracts in High-Citation Papers:** High-citation papers often have well-crafted abstracts that cover the study's objectives, methodologies, and findings comprehensively, making them rich in keywords and contextual content. When embeddings are generated from these abstracts, they may be contextually richer, leading to higher similarity scores with other similarly comprehensive abstracts.

Investigating the top 10% of highly cited documents among the most similar papers shows that some semi-high-cited papers have reoccurred in the list of the most lexically similar set for 1% to nearly 10% of papers. Although this is not a prevalent pattern and there's no significant correlation between high-citedness and recognition as the most lexically similar paper (reason 1 is not effective), this overrepresentation of these highly cited papers can be more problematic in high-granularity analysis.

When examining these reoccurring papers as the most similar, many of them, particularly the high-cited ones, are review types, rich in keywords such as "comprehensive review", "from...to...", "paper reviews...", "literature", "towards...", "summarizes", "Trends in", "A rift into", "advances in". Additionally, These publications, besides reviews, tend to have other types of mentions indicating recency (like "recent", and "latest") or are rich in diverse keywords, especially in multidisciplinary studies, with rather longer abstracts (reason 4), making them more likely to be recognized as lexically similar to other papers.

To increase the homogeneity of the keywords affecting LLM decisions, we normalize our calculations both by document type (as each type comprises a specific set of keywords and some types like reviews generally receive more citation) and by thematic clusters (each representing a subject area with its related keywords). This normalization aims to improve the expected citation ratio estimation.

Normalizing by document type means that, within each cluster and period, each paper's citations are estimated based on the weighted citations of the most similar papers only from the same document type as the document itself. For example, a review paper would be compared only with the citations of other review papers that share the most lexical similarity. Similarly, normalization by cluster means within each time window and cluster, papers are only compared with their most lexically similar papers within the same thematic cluster as themselves.

In comparison, results from normalization by cluster (Figure) show better outcomes during the early years, suggesting an improvement in overestimation. On the other hand, normalization by document type (Figure) has performed better in recent year windows, minimizing underestimation and keeping the expected citation ratio closer to 1.

Figure 3. Cosine-Weighted Expected Citation Ratio Normalized to Cluster

Cluster	2001-2003	2004-2006	2007-2009	2010-2012	2013-2015	2016-2018	2019-2021
0	0.49	0.56	0.66	0.71	0.81	0.90	1.14
1	0.77	0.85	0.90	0.95	0.93	0.97	1.05
2	0.84	0.93	1.06	0.99	0.91	0.90	0.88
3	0.46	0.54	0.61	0.69	0.83	1.05	1.11
4	0.22	0.31	0.53	0.67	0.88	1.00	1.04
5	0.48	0.57	0.73	0.79	0.86	0.93	0.89
6	0.55	0.65	0.79	0.86	0.84	0.95	1.12
7	0.49	0.62	0.68	0.78	0.76	0.89	1.03
8	0.74	0.77	0.82	0.78	0.85	0.90	1.10
9	0.76	0.75	1.05	0.96	0.88	0.84	0.80
10	0.89	0.89	0.87	0.94	0.96	0.96	0.91
11	0.30	0.35	0.51	0.62	0.76	0.97	1.25
12	0.26	0.34	0.57	0.60	0.76	0.90	1.14
13	1.01	0.74	0.75	0.82	0.76	0.78	1.04
14	1.00	0.91	0.90	0.89	0.86	0.79	0.89
15	0.47	0.58	0.78	0.72	0.77	0.85	0.98
16	0.60	0.70	0.74	0.75	0.75	0.88	1.13
17	0.67	0.78	0.81	0.92	0.98	1.02	1.06
18	0.42	0.61	0.76	0.72	0.86	0.95	1.09
19	0.61	0.66	0.90	0.88	0.85	0.83	0.93
20	0.31	0.36	0.64	1.04	0.93	0.94	0.80
21	0.22	0.31	0.49	0.53	0.67	0.97	1.06
22	0.37	0.49	0.63	0.80	0.94	0.97	1.01
23	0.36	0.42	0.80	0.92	0.82	0.76	0.95
24	0.52	0.65	0.68	0.68	0.85	1.04	1.04
25	0.74	0.77	0.87	0.88	1.06	1.17	1.07
26	1.00	0.76	1.51	0.87	0.92	0.84	0.79
27	0.43	0.62	0.64	0.68	0.89	1.05	1.15
28	0.15	0.19	0.30	0.38	0.75	0.96	0.96

Figure 4. Cosine-Weighted Expected Citation Ratio Normalized to Document Type

Cluster	2001-2003	2004-2006	2007-2009	2010-2012	2013-2015	2016-2018	2019-2021
0	0.51	0.58	0.69	0.70	0.81	0.91	1.11
1	0.76	0.84	0.88	0.92	0.91	0.97	1.03
2	0.83	0.92	1.04	0.98	0.93	0.91	0.89
3	0.47	0.54	0.61	0.70	0.81	1.07	1.13
4	0.24	0.33	0.55	0.70	0.87	1.00	1.06
5	0.53	0.63	0.79	0.83	0.91	1.01	0.94
6	0.55	0.65	0.78	0.81	0.85	0.95	1.11
7	0.52	0.68	0.72	0.81	0.81	0.97	1.07
8	0.75	0.78	0.83	0.77	0.82	0.90	1.07
9	0.89	0.89	1.18	1.08	0.96	0.88	0.85
10	0.87	0.87	0.85	0.89	0.93	0.93	0.89
11	0.30	0.36	0.53	0.61	0.74	0.97	1.23
12	0.27	0.36	0.58	0.61	0.73	0.91	1.15
13	1.05	0.79	0.80	0.80	0.78	0.83	1.07
14	1.01	0.92	0.90	0.87	0.86	0.83	0.93
15	0.53	0.64	0.85	0.76	0.81	0.94	1.05
16	0.69	0.77	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.92	1.13
17	0.69	0.79	0.82	0.90	0.95	1.05	1.07
18	0.45	0.64	0.79	0.74	0.85	0.97	1.10
19	0.62	0.68	0.93	0.90	0.88	0.87	0.98
20	0.40	0.46	0.75	1.19	1.05	1.02	0.85
21	0.23	0.32	0.53	0.55	0.68	0.99	1.07
22	0.45	0.57	0.72	0.84	1.00	1.04	1.04
23	0.38	0.43	0.83	1.00	0.82	0.77	1.01
24	0.56	0.66	0.67	0.70	0.85	1.05	1.01
25	0.76	0.78	0.86	0.90	0.96	1.16	1.05
26	1.08	0.85	1.65	0.99	1.01	0.93	0.89
27	0.45	0.67	0.68	0.70	0.87	1.04	1.16
28	0.18	0.22	0.33	0.45	0.79	1.11	1.06

Considering the impact of publication year on the estimation of expected citations, we finally normalized by publication year. This means within each cluster and publication year window, each document is only compared with the most lexically similar publications with less than a three-year absolute difference in their publication years.

The Figure shows the ultimate version of the model, estimating the Citation Ratio of papers across clusters and publication year windows, normalized by publication year, thematic cluster, and document type. This model provides the best results compared to previous versions, with expected citation rates closest to 1, indicating more accurate estimations. One of the drawbacks

of the environment-based approaches is that the environment-normalized citation score for the complete set will not be guaranteed to be equal to 1 as with the journal and field expected citation scores.

Figure 5. Cosine-Weighted Expected Citation Ratio Normalized to Document Type, Cluster, and Publication-Year Vicinity

Cluster	2001-2003	2004-2006	2007-2009	2010-2012	2013-2015	2016-2018	2019-2021
0	0.9	0.88	0.93	0.85	0.84	0.83	0.98
1	0.92	0.91	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.99
2	0.9	0.9	0.93	0.91	0.91	0.9	0.97
3	0.97	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.84	0.87	1
4	0.92	0.84	0.87	0.85	0.85	0.87	0.96
5	0.93	0.86	0.88	0.86	0.84	0.87	0.93
6	0.89	0.89	0.88	0.85	0.87	0.87	0.97
7	0.94	0.94	0.9	0.92	0.89	0.86	0.97
8	0.91	0.89	0.92	0.89	0.88	0.84	0.95
9	1.01	0.87	0.94	0.88	0.87	0.85	0.93
10	0.91	0.9	0.87	0.83	0.87	0.93	1
11	0.93	0.86	0.93	0.89	0.86	0.85	1.01
12	0.94	0.81	0.92	0.84	0.82	0.82	0.98
13	0.98	0.9	0.92	0.92	0.88	0.81	0.88
14	0.92	0.88	0.9	0.89	0.88	0.85	0.96
15	0.89	0.84	0.91	0.83	0.85	0.85	0.95
16	0.9	0.91	0.91	0.88	0.87	0.85	0.98
17	0.91	0.93	0.9	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.97
18	0.89	0.91	0.93	0.88	0.89	0.86	0.99
19	0.96	0.91	0.88	0.86	0.88	0.86	0.97
20	0.91	0.89	0.86	0.89	0.86	0.91	0.92
21	0.86	0.77	0.88	0.83	0.81	0.81	0.91
22	0.95	0.89	0.9	0.9	0.92	0.89	0.98
23	0.95	0.95	0.83	0.85	0.84	0.82	0.94
24	0.9	1.01	0.94	0.92	0.88	0.9	0.95
25	1	0.91	0.98	0.94	0.87	0.97	1.03
26	0.92	0.86	1.26	0.88	0.96	0.93	0.97
27	0.91	0.97	0.89	0.86	0.89	0.9	1.02
28	0.93	1	0.85	0.68	0.77	0.86	1

The results of the correlation analysis (Figure 6) confirm that while controlling for publication year vicinity and document type significantly improves citation estimation, incorporating thematic clusters further enhances the accuracy, highlighting the importance of combining all factors for the best results.

Figure 6. Pearson's Correlation Between Actual Citations and The Expected Citations from Different Estimation Models

Estimation Model	Correlation
Cosine-Weighted Expected Citation	0.4
Cosine-Weighted Expected Citation Normalized to Document Type	0.44
Cosine-Weighted Expected Citation Normalized to Cluster	0.41
Cosine-Weighted Expected Citation Normalized to Document Type and Publication Year Vicinity	0.53
Cosine-Weighted Expected Citation Normalized to Document Type, Cluster, and Publication Year Vicinity	0.55

4. Conclusion and Future Work

Our study on expected citation impact in circular economy research revealed the benefits of using Large Language Models to create lexical relationships between papers, enabling the creation of environments or clusters that share common themes. This clustering approach allows for a more granular analysis, contrasting with traditional journal-based or subject-based standards. The expected citation rates were derived from cosine-weighted citation counts, and normalization to publication year, thematic clusters, and document type improves the results of estimation significantly.

However, utilizing LLMs to establish lexical similarities is a relatively new method and requires further exploration. The outcomes suggest that these models, trained on our corpora, have

learned patterns that can be useful in bibliometric analysis, but their exact functioning demands a deeper understanding. Techniques like model explainability and sensitivity analysis could help assess whether inherent biases affect how the LLM selects words or phrases.

While the model's outcomes were promising, several areas require future investigation. First, examining other measures of similarity besides cosine could mitigate the impact of high-dimensionality, where minor variations might lead to significant ranking shifts, potentially causing over- or underestimation. Additionally, the selection of the top 100 similar papers could be refined by introducing a mechanism for random sampling among high-similarity candidates, reducing outlier effects. This method could provide a more varied and potentially less biased set of similar papers.

5. Bibliographic References

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6. Appendix

Appendix a. Labeling 29 Clusters Within the Circular Economy Literature for an ECOOM Internal Report Purpose, which is previously published

Cluster ID	Cluster Name
0	Behavioral Change
1	Water, Marine Biology, Fish & Fisheries
2	Threads of non-circular activities on ecosystems
3	Sustainable Manufacturing/Operations Research
4	Building & Construction: Energy Efficiency
5	Energy & Fuels, Biofuels, Hydrogen
6	Negative Effects in Agriculture
7	Materials: Circular Plastics and BioPlastics
8	Pollution: Toxicity & contamination
9	Nanoparticles: impact on life cycles
10	Life cycles of Organisms
11	Cements & Concrete: building materials
12	Sustainable Energy consumption in Transportation and Manufacturing
13	Bacteria & Viruses
14	Plant Genomics
15	Heavy Metals in Waste
16	Reuse of Biomaterials
17	Water: usage, fresh water, sewage, waste
18	Water: Recycling or treatment of wastewater
19	Biomaterials & Bioconversion
20	Batteries
21	Economics, Customer Behavior Sustainable Business Models
22	Membranes for purification & desalination
23	production of bio-products: biorefineries
24	Sustainable Manufacturing
25	Control & Aerial
26	Ionic Liquids for carbon capture
27	Wind, Wave, and tidal Energy
28	Microplastics